

Organic amendment treatments for resistome risk reduction in soil-crop systems

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Supplementary Table S1. Physicochemical properties of the organic amendments studied in the preliminary experiment.

Property	Compost	Manure	Slurry
Dry matter (%)	32.61	22.42	6.56
Electrical conductivity (mS cm⁻¹)	1.03	1.08	1.00
pH	8.69	8.91	8.67
Organic matter (% DW)	66.23	86.74	78.27
Organic C (%)	12.56	11.31	2.99
N (%)	1.00	0.58	0.32
C/N	12.56	20.56	29.85
K₂O (% DW)	2.10	3.10	4.44
P₂O₅ (% DW)	0.59	0.70	1.16
Cd (mg kg⁻¹ DW)	0.15	0.06	0.14
Co (mg kg⁻¹ DW)	1.68	1.40	3.25
Cr (mg kg⁻¹ DW)	7.06	6.74	7.08
Cu (mg kg⁻¹ DW)	55.31	50.71	116.94
Ni (mg kg⁻¹ DW)	10.63	4.61	10.78
Pb (mg kg⁻¹ DW)	2.72	1.44	2.76
Zn (mg kg⁻¹ DW)	203.07	193.97	441.4

Supplementary Table S2. Primers and PCR conditions for droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) analysis.

Gene	Primers	Amplicon size (bp)	Cycling conditions	Reference
16S rRNA	F: CCTACGGGAGGCAGCAG R: ATTACCGCGGCTGCTGG	194	95 °C for 5 min 40 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s and 60 °C for 1 min, with a ramping rate of 2.5 °C s ⁻¹ 4 °C for 5 min 90 °C for 5 min	(1)
tetA	F: GCTACATCCTGCTTGCCTTC R: CATAGATCGCCGTGAAGAGG	210	95 °C for 5 min 40 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s and 62.5 °C for 1 min, with a ramping rate of 2.5 °C s ⁻¹ 4 °C for 5 min 90 °C for 5 min	(2)
tetX	F: AGCCTTACCAATGGGTGTAAA R: TTCTTACCTTGGACATCCCG	278	95 °C for 5 min 40 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s and 57.5 °C for 1 min, with a ramping rate of 2.5 °C s ⁻¹ 4 °C for 5 min 90 °C for 5 min	(3)
sul1	F: CCGTTGGCCTTCCTGTAAAG R: TTGCCGATCGCGTGAAGT	67	95 °C for 5 min 40 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s and 60 °C for 1 min, with a ramping rate of 2.5 °C s ⁻¹ 4 °C for 5 min 90 °C for 5 min	(4)
sul2	F: CGGCTGCGCTTCGATT R: CGCGCGCAGAAAGGATT	60	95 °C for 5 min 40 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s and 60 °C for 1 min, with a ramping rate of 2.5 °C s ⁻¹ 4 °C for 5 min 90 °C for 5 min	(5)
intl1	F: GCCTTGATGTTACCCGAGAG R: GATCGGTCTGAATGCCTGT	196	95 °C for 5 min 40 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s and 61 °C for 1 min, with a ramping rate of 2.5 °C s ⁻¹ 4 °C for 5 min 90 °C for 5 min	(6)
tnpA-04	F: CCGATCACGAAAGCTCAAG R: GGCTCGCATGACTTCGAATC	101	95 °C for 5 min 40 cycles of 95 °C for 30 s and 61 °C for 1 min, with a ramping rate of 2.5 °C s ⁻¹ 4 °C for 5 min 90 °C for 5 min	(7)

Supplementary Table S3. Primer sets used in high-throughput qPCR (HT-qPCR) analysis.

Gene	Forward Primer	Reverse Primer	Target antibiotics (major)
16S rRNA	GGGTTGCGCTCGTTGC	ATGGYTGTCGTCAGCTCGTG	16S rRNA
Bacteroidetes	GGARCATGTGGTTTAATTCGATGAT	AGCTGACGACAACCATGCAG	Taxonomic
Firmicutes	GGAGYATGTGGTTTAATTCGAAGCA	AGCTGACGACAACCATGCAC	Taxonomic
aac(3)-iid_ia	CGATGGTCCGGTTGGTC	TCGGCGTAGTGCAATGCG	Aminoglycoside
aac(6)-ig	GCGATGTTAGAAGCCTCAATTCG	CACACTTCGGCCTGTGCGAA	Aminoglycoside
aac(6)-ir	GCTATAACGATCAGCAGCAAGC	CGCGATGCATGGCATGAC	Aminoglycoside
aac(6)-is_iu_ix	AAGCTTACTCTGGCCTGATCATG	TGCCTGAACGTCGATATTCAGG	Aminoglycoside
aac(6')-Iy	GCCTCAATCCGCCACGATTA	ACGCGCTCTGTTTCCTCAA	Aminoglycoside
aac3-IVa	CCAACACGACGCTGCATC	GCTGTCCGCCACAATGTGCG	Aminoglycoside
aac6-aph2	CCAAGAGCAATAAGGGCATACCAA	GCCACACTATCATAACCACTACCG	Aminoglycoside
aadA1	TGTACGGCTCCGCAGTG	CACGGAATGATGTCGTCGTTG	Aminoglycoside
aadA16	ACGGTGGCCTGAAGCC	GAATTGCAGTCCCGTCTGG	Aminoglycoside
aadA5	ATCACGATCTTGGCATTTTGCT	CTGCGGATGGGCCTAGAAG	Aminoglycoside
aadA6	CCATCGAGCGTCATCTGGAA	CCCGTCTGGCCGGATAAC	Aminoglycoside
aadA7	CACTCCGCGCCTTGGA	TGTGGCGGGCTCGAAG	Aminoglycoside
aadB	CCTGCTTGGTGGGCAGAC	CGGCACGCAAGACCTCAA	Aminoglycoside
aph3-III	CAGAAGGCAATGTCATACCACTTG	GACAGCCGCTTAGCCGAA	Aminoglycoside
aph4-Ib	GGGAACACCGTGCTCACC	GTTGGTCCCGTGCAAGTC	Aminoglycoside
aph6-Ia	CGCTGGGAGCTGAAGAGG	AGCATCGTGCTGCTCTCC	Aminoglycoside
apmA	GGCGCATATGCATTCATCA	CTATACTCCAGTCCCACCATTGA	Aminoglycoside
armA	TCTTCGACGAATGAAAGAGTCG	GCTAATGGATTGAAGCCACAACC	Aminoglycoside
spcN	GCTATGTGCTGGTGGACTGG	GGAACCACTCGACGAACTCG	Aminoglycoside
strB	GCTCGGTGCTGAGAACAATCT	CAATTTCCGGTCGCTGGTAGT	Aminoglycoside
bla1	GCAAGTTGAAGCGAAAGAAAAGA	TACCAGTATCAATCGCATATACACCTAA	β -lactam
blaACT	AAGCCGCTCAAGCTGGA	GCCATATCCTGCACGTTGG	β -lactam
blaBEL-nonmobile	ATGTCCATGGCACAGACTGTG	CCTGTCTTGTCACCCGTTACC	β -lactam
blaMIR	CGGTCTGCCGTTACAGGTG	AAAGACCCGCGTCGTCATG	β -lactam
blaOXY_1	CGTTCAGGCGGCAGGTT	GCCGCGATATAAGATTGAGAATT	β -lactam
blaOXY_2	AAAGGTGACCGCATTTCGC	CCAGCGTCAGCTTGCG	β -lactam
blaSFO	CCGCCGCCATCCAGTA	GGGCCGCCAAGATGCT	β -lactam
cphA	GCGAGCTGCACAAGCTGAT	CGGCCAGTCGCTCTTC	β -lactam
intI1_1	CGAACGAGTGGCGGAGGGTG	TACCCGAGAGCTTGGCACCCA	Integrans
intI1_2	CGAAGTCGAGGCATTTCTGTC	GCCTTCCAGAAAACCGAGGA	Integrans
intI3	CAGGTGCTGGGCATGGA	CCTGGGCAGCATCACCA	Integrans
acrA	GGTCTATCACCTACGCGCTATC	GCGCGCACGAACATAACC	MDR
cefa_qacelta	TAGTTGGCGAAGTAATCGCAAC	TGCGATGCCATAACCGATTATG	MDR
czcA	GCCTTGTTTCATCGGCGAAC	GGCAATGTGCTCCTTCGTTTC	MDR
emrD	CTCAGCAGTATGGTGGTAAGCATT	ACCAGGCGCCGAAGAAC	MDR

mepA	ATCGGTGCTCTTCGTTAC	ATAAATAGGATCGAGCTGCTGGAT	MDR
oprD	ATGAAGTGGAGGCCATTG	GGCCACGGCGAACTGA	MDR
pbrT	GATGCGCACTGGGCTTG	TCGGAATATGCGGAAATGCG	MDR
sugE	CTTAGTTATTGCTGGTCTGCTGGA	GCATCGGGTTAGCGGACTC	MDR
ttgA	ACGCCAATGCCAAACGATT	GTCACGGCGCAGCTTGA	MDR
IncN_rep	AGTTCACCACCTACTCGCTCCG	CAAGTTCTTCTGTTGGGATTCCG	MGE
IS1111	GTCTTAAGGTGGGCTGCGTG	CCCCGAATCTCATTGATCAGC	MGE
IS1133	GCAGCGTCGGGTTGGA	ACGCGTTCGAACAACACTGTAATG	MGE
IS1247_1	CGGCCGTCCTGACCAA	TCGGCAGGTTGGTGACG	MGE
IS1247_2	TGGATCGACCGGTTCCAT	GCTGACCGAGCTGTCCATGT	MGE
IS6100	CGCACCGGCTTGATCAGTA	CTGCCACGCTCAATACCGA	MGE
IS630	CCGCCACCAGTGTGATGG	TTGGCGCTGACTGGATGC	MGE
ISEcp1	CATGCTCTGCGGTCCTTC	GACGCACCTTCTTGATGACC	MGE
ISPps	CACACTGCAAAAACGCATCCT	TGTCTTTGGCGTCACAGTTCTC	MGE
orf37-IS26	GCCGGGTTGTGCAAATAGAC	TGGCAATCTGTGCTGCTG	MGE
Tn5403	AAGCGAATGGCGCGAAC	CGCGCAGGGTAAACTGC	MGE
tnpA_2	CCGATCACGGAAAGCTCAAG	GGCTCGCATGACTTCGAATC	MGE
tnpA_3	GGGCGGTCGATTGAAA	GTGGGCGGGATCTGCTT	MGE
trbC	CGGYATWCCGSCSACRCTGCG	GCCACCTGYSBGCAGTCMCC	MGE
ereA	GATAATTCTGCTGGCGACA	GCAGGCGTGGTCACAAC	MLSB
erm35	CCTTCAGTCAGAACCGCAA	GCTGATTTGACAGTTGGTGGTG	MLSB
erm36	GGCGGACCGACTTGCAAT	TCTGCGTTGACGACGGTTAC	MLSB
ermE	GTCACGCAGCTGGAGTTCG	CGGTGAAGCACAGCTCGAC	MLSB
ermO	GAGTACGCCCCGAAACG	GCGTTCGATCCGGAGGA	MLSB
ermX	TGATGACGGCTCAGTGG	GTGACCAGCGCCTGA	MLSB
lnuB	GGATCGTTTACCAAAGGAGAAGG	AGCATAGCCTTCGTATCAGGAA	MLSB
lnuC	GGGTGTAGATGCTCTTCTTGGGA	CTTTACCCGAAAAGAGTTTCTACCG	MLSB
mefA_1	TAATTATCGCAGCAGCTGGTTC	GTTCCCAAACGGAGTATAAGAGTG	MLSB
mefA_2	CCGTAGCATTGGAACAGCTTTT	AAACGGAGTATAAGAGTGCTGCAA	MLSB
mphA	TCAGCGGGATGATCGACTG	GAGGGCGTAGAGGGCGTA	MLSB
oleC	CCCGGAGTCGATGTTTCA	GCCGAAGACGTACACGAACAG	MLSB
pncA	GCAATCGAGGCGGTGTTT	TTGCCGACGCAATTCA	MLSB
vat(A)	ATGAACGGAGCGAATCATCGG	CCATACCGATCCAAACGTCATTTT	MLSB
bacA	ATCCGCGCACCCCTGA	CCTGCTTGATGGACTTGATGAAGA	Other
fabK	CAGGAGCAGGAAATCCAAGC	CCAGCTTCCATTCTCTTCTGC	Other
mcr1	CACATCGACGGCGTATTCTG	CAACGAGCATAACCGACATCG	Other
merA	GTGCCGTCCAAGATCATG	GGTGAAGTCCAGTAGGGTGA	Other
ttgB	TCGCCCTGGATGTACACCTT	ACCATTGCCGACATCAACAAC	Other
catQ	AGGTGCACTTACAGTATGACTGC	AACGTGGGAAGTTCTCGTCATAC	Phenicol
cmlV	GCCCTCATCACCGTCTTCG	GGACGTTGGCGATGGAGAG	Phenicol
optrA	GGTGGATGAAGTCCGTACGG	AGGTTAGACCTCCAAGAGCCA	Phenicol
qepA	GGGCATCGCGCTGTTT	GCGCATCGGTGAAGCC	Quinolone
qnrB	GCGACGTTTCAAGTGGTTCAGA	GCTGCTCGCCAGTCGAA	Quinolone

qnrB4	TCACCACCCGCACCTG	GGATATCTAAATCGCCCAGTTCC	Quinolone
sul3	TCCGTTTACAGCAATTGGTGACG	TTCGTTTACGCCTTACACCAGC	Sulfonamide
tetD	AATTGCACTGCCTGCATTGC	GACAGATTGCCAGCAGCAGA	Tetracycline
tetG	TCGCGTTCCTGCTTGCC	CCGCGAGCGACAAACCA	Tetracycline
tetL	ATGGTTGTAGTTGCGCGCTATAT	ATCGCTGGACCGACTCCTT	Tetracycline
tetM	GGAGCGATTACAGAATTAGGAAGC	TCCATATGTCCTGGCGTGTC	Tetracycline
tetPA	GGAAACCTTAGTTCAGTGACTTGG	CCCATTTAACCACGCACTGAA	Tetracycline
tetPB	TGGGCGACAGTAGGCTTAGAA	TGACCCTACTGAAACATTAGAAATATACCT	Tetracycline
tetR	CCGTCAATGCGCTGATGAC	GCCAATCCATCGACAATCACC	Tetracycline
tetW	ATGAACATTCCCACGTTATCTTT	ATATCGGGCGGAGAGCTTATCC	Tetracycline
dfrA27	GCCGCTCAGGATCGGTA	GTCGAGATATGTAGCGTGTCG	Trimethoprim
vanA	GGGCTGTGAGGTCGGTTG	TTCAGTACAATGCGGCCGTTA	Vancomycin
vanB	TTGTCGGCGAAGTGGATCA	AGCCTTTTTCCGGCTCGTT	Vancomycin
vanHB	GAGGTTTCCGAGGCGACAA	CTCTCGGGCGGAGTCGTAT	Vancomycin
vanTC	ACAGTTGCCGCTGGTGAAG	CGTGGCTGGTCGATCAAAA	Vancomycin

Supplementary Table S4. Comparison of the relative abundances of antibiotic resistance genes and mobile genetic element genes in soil (S) and lettuce (L) samples for each treatment, based on Tukey's post-hoc test. ns: not significant; *: $p < 0.05$; **: $p < 0.01$; ***: $p < 0.001$.

Gene	Untreated compost	Anaerobic digestion	Biochar compost	Biochar soil	NPK	Unamended
aac(6)-Ig	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L **	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L *
aac3-IVa	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L *	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L **
aadA5	S > L *	ns	ns	ns	ns	S > L *
blaBEL-nonmobile	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
cmlV	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L **	S > L ***	S > L *	S > L ***
czcA	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L **	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L **
erm35	S > L **	S > L *	S > L *	S > L **	S > L **	S > L **
ermX	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L **
fabK	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L *
intI1_1	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L **
intI1_2	ns	ns	ns	S > L *	ns	ns
IS6100	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L **	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L *
ISEcp1	S > L ***	S > L *	S > L **	S > L **	S > L **	S > L **
mefA	S > L ***	S > L *	S > L **	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L *
mepA	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L ***	S > L **
optrA	S > L ***	S > L *	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L ***
orf37-IS26	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L ***	ns	S > L ***	S > L **
spcN	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L **	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L ***
tetPA	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
ttgA	S > L ***	S > L *	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L ***	S > L **

Supplementary Figure S1. Relative abundance (via HT-qPCR analysis) of antibiotic resistance genes and mobile genetic element genes in the studied soils.

Supplementary Figure S2. Relative abundance (via HT-qPCR analysis) of antibiotic resistance genes and mobile genetic element genes in lettuce samples.

Supplementary Figure S3. The 30 most abundant bacterial classes in the studied soils.

Supplementary Figure S4. Principal coordinates analysis (PCoA) plot of soil microbial community composition based on Bray-Curtis distance metric for bacterial class in the studied soils.

References

1. Muyzer, G., de Waal, E. C. & Uitterlinden, A. G. Profiling of complex microbial populations by denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis analysis of polymerase chain reaction-amplified genes coding for 16S rRNA. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* **59**, 695–700 (1993).
2. Ng, L. K., Martin, I., Alfa, M. & Mulvey, M. Multiplex PCR for the detection of tetracycline resistant genes. *Mol. Cell Probes* **15**, 209–215 (2001).
3. Diehl, D. L. & Lapara, T. M. Effect of temperature on the fate of genes encoding tetracycline resistance and the integrase of class 1 integrons within anaerobic and aerobic digesters treating municipal wastewater solids. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **44**, 9128–9133 (2010).
4. Heuer, H. & Smalla, K. Manure and sulfadiazine synergistically increased bacterial antibiotic resistance in soil over at least two months. *Environ. Microbiol.* **9**, 657–666 (2007).
5. Heuer, H. *et al.* Fate of sulfadiazine administered to pigs and its quantitative effect on the dynamics of bacterial resistance genes in manure and manured soil. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* **40**, 1892–1900 (2008).
6. Barraud, O., Baclet, M. C., Denis, F. & Ploy, M. C. Quantitative multiplex real-time PCR for detecting class 1, 2 and 3 integrons. *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.* **65**, 1642–1645 (2010).
7. Zhu, Y.G. *et al.* Diverse and abundant antibiotic resistance genes in Chinese swine farms. *P. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **110**, 3435–3440 (2013).